

THE SENSE OF PATRIOTISM IN THE WORKS OF ABDULLA AVLONI FORMATION

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Safarbayeva Ruzakhon Nabijonovna
TDPU, BT Phrase student

Annotation: *This article talks about the great thinker, pedagogue, one of the exponents, of modern literature, Abdulla Avloni, about advantages of forming a sense of patriotism and applying it to the youth of the present time and the future generation.*

Key words: *thinker, education, manners, behavior, sense of patriotism future generation, student, pedagogue, creator.*

When we mention the figure of Abdulla Avloni, in the eyes of everyone, a great thinker pedagogue, founder of education is embodied for many centuries, our people have recognized Abdulla avloni as a great pedagogue.

Indeed Abdulla Avloni's thoughts worldviews and pedagogical recommendations on education have come to the attention of the people and today, and higher education institutions. Now, in addition to Avloni's writings about education manners, manners, and the following sentences, if we turn to his works on educating students young people of the future generation based on the sense of patriotism making young people love the Motherland, what is the Motherland. That is in the work of Abdulla Avloni called "Turkiy Guliston yokhud akhloq" it is said that to love motherland" motherland is the city and country where a person was born and grew up, that person's homeland is called his homeland even animals have this sense of homeland.

If this animal loses its homeland, it will not live as comfortably as it did in its own land, its life will be miserable, and it will always be in the corner of its mouth. To love of one's country remains our grandfathers said, "Be a shepherd in your own country until there is a sultan in another's country".

Our beloved Messenger, may god bless him and grant him peace, said: Hubbul's motherland is faith.

Don't worry, this country will remain for my generation
I don't feel sad when the bubble is blowing, but
I am afraid that my country is my own country
I was born and grew up, this is my country
I wonder if it will be the original roje if it dies.

Defined as it follows from this poem that even if I lose my body and soul for the Motherland. I have no sorrow for my generation, this is my homeland, even if my sorrow is full of dust, I have fear in my body, I have ruler in my homeland. The writer expresses the spirit of patriotism in his heart by saying "ru kafanim vujudimhok" to the place where I was born and raised in these and similar works and poems of Avloni patriotic feelings are explained and described in a simple and fluent language. It is possible to use not only

Avoni's thoughts and works of other poets to form a sense of patriotism in young the future generation of schoolchildren. At present the first topic of the 1 st grade is praise worthy. If every child born and raised in our country das not have the faling of love for the motherland in his heart. He will look like a cruel person. Our forefathers who loved in eirlair times did not say for nothing that “ The homeland begins at the threshold; when a child leaves school, the family they live in is thought that is a small country.

The meaning of the world is reflected n the poem “Homeland” included in the first volume of “selected works”. Of Abdulla Avloni, published in 2009.

Your name is sacred in this world,
 Everyone das not know your value.
 Your feeling makes a trade in
 Hearts, your pain takes away other pain
 Your land and water feed us and
 Feed us, and laughter your fat
 Fat sheep, Apples, figs grapes
 Your oxen, your goats, your donkeys
 All of them serve for us eack of
 Them is a small piece of blessing.
 I was born from you, grew up went back
 We will let you in again,
 You are our mother! You are our wonderful mother!
 You are our room...(2)

It can be understand from this poem that the feeling of the Motherland, eating the delicacies of this land, and living in the bosom of the Motherland is reflected the poet describes the motherand as “you are our mother, you are ourl devoted “ mother.

To the wise words of Abdulla Avloni written on the basis of patriotic feeling in these and several other works, poems and other works of Abdulla Avloni instructive, wise, definition, we face pedagogical views. Every artist should have the feeling of the Motherland in his heart while creating needed. He should have a heart, a sense of beauty. It is impossible to write about it without loving the country, it is impossible to describe it. That`s why every artist when he takes a pen in his hand, first of all sings about his Motherland. People living in this country will be at peace only if the country is peaceful. Since we live in a peaseful time, we need to teach every child the feeling of gratitude. Of course, this should be explained and instilled into the . student`s heart from the school age, even from child hood, with the valuable words of the thinkers of pedagogic sciences, especially.

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